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**NATIONAL ACTION GAMES IN PRIMARY GRADE PHYSICAL EDUCATION
SCIENCE**

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Abstract – In the science of Elementary School Physical Education, the importance of national action games, the procedure for conducting national and action games and the methods of interest, attraction and application of elementary students in the course of classes are considered..

Keywords: elementary grade, physical education, national game, action game.

INTRODUCTION

The development of national action games, folk games held in training, holidays remain a new and indelible page in the history of Uzbek spiritual and Physical Culture. The torch, which was first lit at the festival of the people's games in Forish, provided an opportunity to restore the long-standing play-by-play traditions in many parts of our Republic. If the holiday” people's games " of 1990 was held when two villages – Sayyad and United, then 1992 and 1993 were organized at the level of the Jizzakh region – with the active participation of all districts of this territory. The Olympiad “people's games” of the I Republic was held here, which was attended by representatives of all regions of our motherland and the Republic of Karakalpakstan. At the Olympics, the long-standing folk

games will be competed in such types as “Storm”, “Jambul” “rider”, “take away”, “Wormwood”, “shoulder wrestling”, “forty stones”, “Donkey rode”, “draw

Working National Action Sports games with children not only in primary education, but also in the period before it gives a good result. These national action games are simple, simple, all playable, fun, and also help a lot to develop valuable human qualities such as strength, agility, dexterity, resourcefulness, resourcefulness, endurance. It is known that the regular involvement of young children in sports makes it possible to develop the child in a healthy way.

When dealing with these games, it is advisable to deal with various action National Games, identifying such characters as the height, weight, structure – figure of the body of the child. It is also organized using testing tools that assess psychological and physical abilities. When teaching a child to a sports qualification, it is necessary that the qualification of the qualification technique be formed, and that there are concepts about the rules of conduct procedures and be constantly engaged.

In this regard, folk games and action games in general have a much lighter effect on the body, as they have educational and social content that distracts children from fatigue. Therefore, these games are very applicable to the improvement of special qualifications inherent in the chosen sport. In the development of physical qualities, however, the importance of Uzbek folk national action games, especially in young children, is limitless. Because performing standard physical exercises over and over again creates situations of rapid exhaustion in the child's body.

This condition comes true as a result of affecting the psyche of the child. The use of national action games during training is of great interest to children, positively affecting their mood and other mental qualities. These conditions, on the other hand, prevent

fatigue complications from occurring earlier in the body, preventing tension situations. Play and collect, study of folk oral creativity and scientific literature.

For example, girls call their friend - Come, comrade, let's play the Frog-frog! - Walk, let's play back! Boys can call by saying the nickname of their comrade: - Stork, let's play out! In some places it is called sharper, more uncompromising: - Will the chicken stay on the roof, Would he shoot from your porch? Children who do not like the game. Train from namazsham? Come-ho, come! Those who are thawed to go out lazily are immediately subject to criticism, children encourage them to independence, to be bold: -

There is cotton in need, Sleep if it comes. Your mother will not dry, Mushday snow does not get enough? Come-ho, come! If the invocation is a girl child, it is called in a slightly gentle tone. Mabodo, the mother of the girl is a stepmother, and although her friends know how to look bad at her daughter, the term does not use the word "stepmother", expressing her dissatisfaction with the gesture - The months were clear, dugana, your play came,. dugona, Or will your mother not leave, dugona, Is your fist belly not full, right?

Choruses are mostly exclaimed, which is an impressive tool, like a flame, which increases the passion for playing in children. There are a lot of types, forms of calling and organizing into the game, we brought only some examples. Its main function is to challenge children to play, tickle their hearts, encourage, remember and strengthen their interests. Engaging these National Action and sports games in the classroom, extracurricular activities process will help the child develop in a healthy way as well as gain insight and information about national, action and folk games.

List of literature used

1. National and action games (educational and methodological manual for students of JTI general course) Tashkent-2009

2. Mirzayeva, D. (2019). THE CONCEPT OF" FRIENDSHIP " IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LINGUISTIC CULTURE. Mirovaya Nauka, (11), 29-32 2.
3. . Usmanxhojayev T.S., Xhojayev.F. Action games. - T., 1992. 5. Usmanxhojayev T.S, Meliyev X. National action games. - T., 2000.
4. Normurodov A N. Uzbek national games. - T., 1999. 7. Usmanxhojayev T.S., X O ja y E v F. 1001 game. - T., 1990.